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An Exploration of Copy Number Variation Between the Sexes

Drosophila melanogaster

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Introduction

Genetic copy number variation (CNV) is of rapidly growing interest to the biological community. It is becoming increasingly clear that CNVs have an enormous impact on evolution and disease, perhaps even more of an impact than what are considered “traditional” mutations, such as single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). Copy number variation occurs when one individual of a species has chromosomes with either extra or missing copies of genes or other pieces of DNA sequence in comparison to the rest of the species. These differences can be as small as a part of a gene, or as large as an entire chromosome. Some of the problems this can cause are exemplified in Down’s Syndrome (trisomy 21) and Huntington’s Disease, where additional copies of a chromosome or simple trinucleotide repeats, respectively, cause clinical pathologies for the affected individual. Ultimately, these disease states are caused by the improper dosage of genetic material, which can lead to improper dosage of proteins, or just incorrectly made proteins. However, CNV does not always have detrimental effects. For example, there is evidence that the alpha and beta hemoglobin genes in humans were originally the same set of genes in only one copy. However, there was a duplication event that copied the original hemoglobin genes onto a new chromosome (Proudfoot *et.al*, 1980). These duplicate genes evolved into the second set of hemoglobin genes. Clearly, in this case, copy number variation has led to a novel adaptation.

In *Drosophila*, there is one example of beneficial CNV that many fly biologists will know. When female *Drosophila* create and lay eggs, they need to coat the egg in its outer protective layer of chorion protein. This process requires a large amount of protein to be produced in a short amount of time. In order to do this, female *Drosophila* endoreduplicate the two chorion loci on chromosomes 3L and X (containing 4 and 2 chorion proteins) as much as 60 times. This only occurs in the follicle cells of the ovaries, and so it must happen for each egg produced. These two CNVs were first brought to the attention of fly biologists by Allan Spradling in 1980 (Spradling & Mahowald, 1980). Spradling knew that the chorion proteins were synthesized very rapidly and that the mRNA was expressed at very high levels during specific time points. He used the female sterile *ocelliless* mutant fly in order to determine where this mutation was and what it was actually doing. The mutation results in a reduction of the chorion proteins produced from the X chromosome (c36 and c38). He used cDNA clones to determine what was missing or added in this mutation. Unexpectedly, he found that in normal flies, the females had amplified levels of those gene sequences and some of the surround DNA, while the mutant fly was missing that amplification. Therefore, increased copy number of the chorion genes was necessary for the normal creation of the *Drosophila melanogaster* eggs (Spradling & Mahowald, 1980).

Since Spradling’s discovery, it was found that the chorion loci are not the only places that endoreduplicate during the egg making process in *Drosophila melanogaster*. The *yellow-g* and *yellow-g2* loci on chromosome 3L amplify four-fold (Claycomb *et.al*, 2004),

and two more loci on chromosome 2L do as well (Kim *et.al*, 2011). These latter two loci contain supporting chorion proteins. The *yellow-g* and *yellow-g2* proteins have been shown to be required for the creation of the structural connections between the chorion and vitelline layers of the egg. Without the amplification of these proteins, the eggs have very weak shells and usually collapse in on themselves right after they are laid. Therefore, all of the so far discovered sex specific CNVs in fruit flies are related to the creation and viability of the egg.

To date, there has been limited research on sex specific CNVs, such as the chorion amplifications. Therefore, I have conducted a full genome examination of male and female *Drosophila melanogaster* in order to identify new sex specific CNVs in this species.

Methods

Materials

I used 36 base single end reads for all lines in Table 1, as well as 76 base paired end reads for w1118, ED776, and Hsp60cED748 lines. The DNA sequences were created by the Illumina Hiseq 2000 from the DrosDel fly lines. These lines are *Drosophila melanogaster* that have had a single hemizygous deletion on the 2L chromosome of each of 21 isogenic lines (Ryder *et.al*, 2007). The deletions span the

chromosome and are nested, such that three deletions remove the same sequence plus a little more for each deletion (Figure 1). The sequences we used were barcoded and analyzed independently by sex, allowing for a comparison of CNVs between males and females. We also used the w1118 line of flies in our analyses. The GEO data accessions for these sequences are listed in Table 1 along with the deletion coordinates on 2L.

I used the reference genomes version 5.54 and 6.01 for *Drosophila melanogaster* (downloaded from Flybase.com) to map the data. I also used the corresponding

Figure 1. Diagram of DrosDel line nested deletions. A) Line 1 has a hemizygous deletion on chromosome 2L that is within the deletion in Line 2, which is in the deletion in Line 3. The other chromosome 2L in each line is normal so that the fly can survive. The nested deletions can allow for the narrowing in of what causes certain traits to happen in flies. B) The male and female read counts for a region are expected to be the same if there is no CNV between the sexes, and (C) the male and female read counts for a region will show a difference if there is a CNV between the sexes. The black line represents the reference genome.

annotations (5.54 and 6.01) for these references in order to determine gene content (downloaded from Flybase.com).

Comparing mapping tools

I mapped five sets of DrosDel whole fly sequencing data (w1118 male and female, ED2809 male and female, ED62 female) with Bowtie 2.2.0 (Langmead & Salzberg, 2012), SHRiMP 2.2.3 (David *et.al*, 2011), and BWA 0.7.7 (Li & Durbin, 2009). I used a number of different options (shown in Table 2) for each tool in order to pick the right set of options as well as the right tool. I then took the mapping results and ran them through GATK (McKenna *et.al*, 2010) in order to compare the SNPs, insertions and deletions, and total number of reads mapped between each mapping program (Table 3).

Mapping male versus female

Using BWA, I mapped all of the data to the *Drosophila melanogaster* reference genome. After mapping, the newly created SAM files then needed to be filtered for mapping quality. The first filtering step was to use samtools 0.1.19 to filter on the mapping quality (MAPQ) value of the SAM file, so that only reads with values greater than 20 were kept. The second step was to filter out the unmapped reads that still had positional information. These reads would cause problems if they were left in for the analysis. I wrote a Python version 2.7 (van Rossum & Drake, 2001) script to look through the SAM (Li *et.al*, 2009) files and remove any reads with a bit flag of 4, meaning that the read was unmapped. I then combined all of the SAM (Li *et.al*, 2009) files created together using the `cat` function, so that they became one file of male sequences and one file of female sequences.

Copy number quantification

In order to count the number of reads mapped at each base, I used samtools mpileup (`samtools mpileup -g -f <reference> <bam_file>`) (Li *et.al*, 2009) to create VCF (Li *et.al*, 2009) files for the male and the female. Figures 1B and 1C show the difference in read depth between males and females with no CNVs between them and males and females with a CNV difference. The samtools mpileup tool provides a count of reads mapped to each base in the genome so that it is possible to compare those counts between males and females statistically. This allowed me to create tables that just included the chromosome, position, and depth at that position. From these tables, I then used Python (version 2.7 and version 3.4) (van Rossum & Drake, 2001) to create prespecified windows across the genome of 10kb in size (so that male and female were comparable). I averaged the number of mapped reads at each position in the window together for an average depth of that window. Finally, I found the sample variance and standard deviation of each mean depth.

Determining content of each 10kb window

I first used the reference genome to obtain a percentage of C and G content in each of my prespecified windows. I then used the BEDtools v2.19.1 intersect command (Quinlan & Hall, 2010) to find the gene content in each window across the genome (`bedtools intersect -a <bed file delimiting window positions> -b <gff> -wa -wb -loj`). The gene content was collected from the annotation GFF file.

Databasing information

In order to make obtaining information easier, I created a database with SQLite (Hipp, 2000) that contained the gene content information organized by chromosome and window. I also added an ontology subset database which allowed me to search for the ontology identifier from the sequence of interest and find out the meaning of that particular ID. This ontology database included both the Sequence Ontology (Elisebeck *et.al*, 2005) and the Gene Ontology (Ashburner *et.al*, 2000). The Gene Ontology is a project that has created structured vocabularies for describing gene products in terms of biological processes, cellular components, and molecular function without referencing species. The Sequence Ontology is a separate controlled vocabulary used to describe the features and attributes of the sequence itself.

Finding significant copy number variation

With the average depths across the 10kb windows I was able to determine which windows contained significant depth changes using R v3.0.1 (R Core Team). I created a log₂ transformation of the data to compare windows to their neighbors. I also used the log₂ transformation for a ratio of male depths to female depths in order to compare male windows to female windows. To determine significance, I used the Student's t-test to determine p-values, adjusting the p-values by the `p.adjust(p-value, method)` package in R. We used the false discovery rate (“fdr”) method. A large sample size causes the p-value to distort so that most samples are significant according to usually used cutoffs. Therefore, 10^{-7} was chosen after observing the 3L chorion amplification to determine when the least amount of noise was present. I supplemented this value by only using windows that had more than half of their length covered by at least one read depth, as well as having a fold change in read number between male and female of 1.2 or more. In order to confirm the significance of the windows I found in R, I used the Integrative Genomics Viewer (IGV) (Robinson *et.al*, 2011). I observed both the male and the female alignments at the positions that looked significant in copy number in order to look for peaks in the read count visualized on IGV.

Comparison of Drosophila melanogaster reference genomes

I used NUCmer, a subset program of MUMmer (Kurtz *et.al*, 2004), in order to determine the differences between the version 5.54 and 6.01 *D. melanogaster* reference genomes. This

allowed me to visualize where different pieces of each chromosome have shifted to in the new version, including where some of the additional sequences that before had not been assigned a chromosome have been placed.

Figure 2. Comparison of male and female read counts by window using reference genome 5.54 across the X chromosome. Top shows the percentage of cytosine and guanine in each 10kb window across each autosome. Any downward spikes can indicate what is likely heterochromatin. Bottom shows the log₂ transformed ratio of male to female read coverage per 10kb window. The female spike contains the chorion 36 and 38 proteins. The male spike (arrow) contains the transposon *gypsy5*.

Results

Comparing mapping tools

The GATK results from each of the SAM files I created showed quite different results for each mapping tool, and even showed quite different results between options of the same mapping tool. I chose which options of the tool to use by comparing the total number of mapped reads between each output (Table 2), since I needed to have high sensitivity for copy number change. Table 3 shows the final comparison between the mapping tools, after the best options had been chosen for each. I wanted to choose a tool that would mapped the most amount of reads back to the reference, since I was looking for CNV and not SNPs. However, I did not want to entirely ignore SNPs while mapping since they could end up being important for the existence of CNVs. Therefore, since SHRiMP showed the most SNPs

and the least mapped reads, and Bowtie 2 showed the most mapped reads and the least SNPs, I decided to use BWA for the rest of my analysis because it mapped enough reads that it was quite close to the Bowtie 2 results, but also showed a much closer number of SNPs to SHRiMP than to Bowtie 2.

Finding male CNV bias

The most extreme male-biased CNV is on the X chromosome between 11,090,000 and 11,100,000 bases and has a fold change of about 2 relative to females (Figure 2). This amplification has a p-value of $2.22e-96$. This peak contains the transposable element *gypsy5* and the gene *CG11106*. In order to determine what element might actually be in different copy number between males and females, I used IGV (Robinson *et.al*, 2011) in

order to visualize where the reads mapped (Figure 3 and 4). I was able to see that the male fly had more reads mapping to the *gypsy5* transposon compared to the female, while the area containing *CG11106* was not different between the two sexes. Since the *gypsy5* transposon is 401bp upstream of *CG11106*, it could be possible that the TE influences the transcription of the gene in some way, particularly since *CG11106* is associated with spermatogenesis, though there is no evidence for this relationship as of now. There is evidence that this transposable element is prevented from jumping around in females because it prefers to jump into the ovo gene, which is necessary for female fertility (Dej *et.al*, 1998). No one has yet investigated males for the same type of control, and this difference in CNV size could suggest a difference in control between female and male flies. There has also been evidence pointing to *gypsy5* being involved in control of the amount of testicular stem cells (Toledano *et.al*, 2012). An siRNA that maps back to *gypsy5* was found as a negative regulator of the integrity of testicular stem cells in male flies. Such a regulatory mechanism could explain why this transposable element varies in abundance between males and females.

Figure 3. IGV image of the male X spike from analysis with reference genome 5.54. This image shows that the *CG11106* gene (in red box) is not included in the amplification in males on the X.

The only other male-biased CNV is located on the very beginning of the chromosome between 20,000 and 230,000 bases and has a fold change of about 1.5 relative to females. This region is very heterochromatic (Figure 2) and so this CNV may not actually be sex biased, but rather the heterochromatin itself may be sex biased. It has been shown that the male flies have less chromatin in the repressive heterochromatin state (Brown & Bachtrog, 2014). This means that during the library creation process, there could be DNA breakage bias towards females. In other words, female samples could have less DNA breakage

Figure 4. IGV image of *gypsy5* insertion on the X chromosome in males and females. The top image shows the depth of coverage of *gypsy5* in males. The coverage on the transposon is twice as much as the normal coverage of the X. The bottom image shows the depth of coverage of *gypsy5* in females which is much closer to the normal X coverage.

because more of the female DNA is tightly packaged as heterochromatin, which is more difficult to break (Cheung *et.al*, 2011). Therefore, during the sequencing process, the males have more sequences available that map to the heterochromatic

region of females. Therefore, this bias may be reflective of a mapping problem due to unequal heterochromatin rather than unequal CNV count. This seems particularly true because there is no real expression difference of the genes in this area between males and females.

Finding female CNV bias

Observing the significant peaks in the ratio of male to female mapped read numbers (Figure 2 and 5), I found a number of female biased amplifications by looking for positions that passed the statistical significance parameters explained in the methods. These amplifications have all already been described by other experiments as mentioned above (Spradling & Mahowald, 1980) (Claycomb *et.al*, 2004) (Kim *et.al*, 2011), however these results show confirmation of the peaks and show that they can still be detected by whole fly sequencing rather than separating tissues.

The first CNV, and arguably most impressive is the chorion protein containing peak on the 3L chromosome, roughly in between 8,670,000 and 8,780,000 bases (Figure 5). This peak shows greater than 4 times as much read coverage in comparison to the male fly

genome. This peak contains 13 genes, including chorion proteins *Cp15*, *Cp16*, *Cp18*, and *Cp19*. The other genes in this peak show no clear expression change in response to the increase in copy number and they also show no expression difference compared to the males. This peak lies between a p-value of $1.97e-155$ and $3.03e-142$ and a mean of $2.17e-143$.

Figure 5. Comparison of male and female read counts by window using reference genome 5.54 across the autosomes. Top shows the percentage of cytosine and guanine in each 10kb window across each autosome. Any downward spikes can indicate what is likely heterochromatin. Bottom shows the log₂ transformed ratio of male to female read coverage per 10kb window. The large female spike on 3L is the chorion 15, 16, 18, and 19 proteins. The small spike on 3L contains *yellow-g* and *yellow-g2*. The two spikes on 2L contain two chorion accessory proteins, which provide direction for the main chorion.

The next CNV is also on the 3L chromosome and shows a much smaller fold change of about 1.2 in comparison to the male (Figure 5). This peak is located roughly between 2,250,000 and 2,290,000 bases on this chromosome and contains the *yellow-g* and *yellow-g2* proteins, which have been shown to be important for the correct linkage of the chorion and vitelline layers of the egg (Claycomb *et.al*, 2004). The amplification lies between a p-value of $1.28e-113$ and $9.26e-166$ and a mean of $4.69e-91$.

On the 2L chromosome there are two more female-specific CNVs (Figure 5). The first one is located between 9,520,000 and 9,580,000 bases, and shows a raw fold change of about 1.2 relative to the male as well. This peak contains *CG13113* and *CG13114*, both

proteins that are accessory chorion proteins and either form part of the structure or help in transporting the chorion to the correct location. This peak is between a p-value of $4.46e-128$ and $5.51e-77$ with a mean of $5.86e-75$.

The other 2L CNV is located between 13,390,000 and 13,430,000 bases and has a fold change of 1.25 relative to the male (Figure 5). This peak contains 10 genes, one of which is *Vm34Ca*, a protein important for vitelline membrane formation. The other genes in this amplification are not associated with reproduction, and also do not show a change in expression relative to the increase in copy number or relative to the male flies. This peak is between a p-value of $5.38e-181$ and $8.49e-130$ with a mean of $2.12e-130$.

Finally, there is one more female CNV located on the X chromosome (Figure 2). This peak contains the other major chorion proteins and has a fold change of about 2.5 in comparison to the male. It is located between 8,340,000 and 8,400,000 bases and contains *Cp36*, *Cp38*, and the *Cp7Fa, b, and c* proteins. It also contains *otu* which is a female germ-line sex determining gene that has been linked to regulation of the endoreduplication (Koryakov *et.al*, 2003). This amplification starts with a p-value of $1.32e-101$ and ends with a p-value of $1.37e-264$ with a mean p-value of $2.2e-102$.

Comparing version 6.01 to version 5.54 *Drosophila melanogaster* reference genome

During my analysis of the CNVs between male fruit flies and female fruit flies using the version 5.54 *D. melanogaster* reference genome, the new *D. melanogaster* genome (version 6.01) was released (downloaded from Flybase.com). I decided that this provided a good opportunity to redo all of my analysis with this new genome and test whether assembly differences impact my data analyses. However, I first decided to find out what was truly different between the two reference genomes. Looking at the NUCmer results (Figure 6) they show that there is a majority of the previously unassigned sequences matching to the centromeric heterochromatin of chromosomes 2

Figure 6. NUCmer Results of a comparison between version 5.54 and version 6.01 of the *Drosophila melanogaster* reference genomes. This is a matrix showing matching sections of sequence from both references. The new version of the genome has moved some of the unmapped sequence onto the centromeres of chromosomes 2 and 3, as well as adding a chromosome Y.

and 3 in the new reference genome. This can also be seen in Figure 7, where the area around the centromeres for these chromosomes shows a male bias. When I compare this to Figure 5, which is from the version 5.54 reference genome, it does not show that same bias. I believe that this bias could be because of the male chromatin arrangement in comparison to the female chromatin arrangement, or that the previous assembly could not handle repeat-rich regions. Finally, the CNV on the beginning of the X from the version 5.54 mapping (Figure 2) failed to show significance, suggesting that the new assignment of sequences has reduced the number of reads mapping to that location. Therefore, these male biases are more likely due to mapping artifacts than actual sex biased CNVs.

Figure 7. Comparison of male and female read counts by window using reference genome 6.01 across the autosomes. Top shows the percentage of cytosine and guanine in each 10kb window across each autosome. Any downward spikes can indicate what is likely heterochromatin. Bottom shows the log₂ transformed ratio of male to female read coverage per 10kb window. The large female spike on 3L is the chorion 15, 16, 18, and 19 proteins. The small spike on 3L contains *yellow-g* and *yellow-g2*. The two spikes on 2L contain two chorion accessory proteins, which provide direction for the main chorion.

Looking at the comparison between Figure 2 and Figure 8, the X chromosome shows the most change towards male bias that is not restricted to centromeric heterochromatin. I recreated my window database with the version 6.01 genome and annotations in order to determine what sequence elements existed in each of these new male biased regions. I

discovered that each of the new male biased windows contained a transposable element, and no other annotations. The identification of a mobile element in the newly annotated male-biased window is reminiscent of the original male biased observation (Figure 2), where the actual CNV was encompassed by the *gypsy5* transposon. I therefore examined each of these windows in IGV in order to make sure that each CNV was indeed due to the

Figure 8. Comparison of male and female read counts by window using reference genome 6.01 across the X chromosome. Top shows the percentage of cytosine and guanine in each 10kb window across each autosome. Any downward spikes can indicate what is likely heterochromatin. Bottom shows the log₂ transformed ratio of male to female read coverage per 10kb window. The female spike contains the chorion 36 and 38 proteins. All of the male spikes away from the ends of the chromosome contain a transposable element.

transposable element. In doing so, I found that these CNVs were indeed because of the transposable elements in the region, however there was a very small number of reads mapped to a very small location on each respective TE. The male fly did have more reads to the TE overall, but with less than 30% of the region actually covered for each new transposon CNV, it is hard to say if this is biological, or just a mapping artifact. With the reads only being 36 bases long, it is possible that the male bias is completely random. Since the only reads mapped were ones that mapped uniquely, it could be pure chance that the male reads in that area had more unique mappings than the female reads. However, this only happening in males is very unlikely to happen randomly, so there is likely to be a biological explanation. In order to further assess the observed lack of reads in these TE regions, I created a graph that showed the actual depths of male and female reads across

the X chromosome rather than the ratio of the log₂ transformed male to female coverage (Figure 9). This confirms the initial assessment in IGV, wherein the male biased regions on the X, ignoring the region containing *gypsy5*, carry a low mapped read count in comparison to the rest of the chromosome. This data also shows that the male has more reads mapping in each CNV region in comparison to the females.

Figure 9. Comparison of male and female read coverage across the X chromosome with reference genome 6.01. The red and blue dots show the actual read coverage numbers across the X chromosome. This is matched with the right sided y-axis. The gray background image is a line version of the log₂ transformed ratios comparing male to female read coverage (from figure #). The orange arrow points to the *gypsy5* amplification, the only one where the male read count is noticeably above the average. The black arrows point to the other male biases transposable elements found. These show that the female has much less mapping than average while the male stays just above the female read count, occasionally also below average.

Discussion

This discovery of male biased transposable elements is only an initial step towards understanding sex-biased CNVs. More work is needed to validate my findings. One of the first things that should be done is remapping the data with a different tool, for example Bowtie 2, in order to determine if the extra reads mapping to the transposable elements will show up with different mapping algorithms. This will make sure that the male biases for TEs is not a mapping artifact.

If the transposable element mapping bias is not an artifact from the mapping process, then the next step would be to discover if there is anything interesting about where these TEs are jumping. If these TEs have a preference for location in the genome, it could indicate why these TEs are active in males and not in females. This could occur for

the same reasons *gypsy5* is suppressed in females. Perhaps these transposons prefer to jump into genes necessary for female function but unnecessary for male function, so only females need to suppress them. It could also be that the male flies need the TEs for some other function, but females do not, and thus suppress the TEs, perhaps to prevent them from destroying another important function. Finally, it could be that the males are actually upregulating the TEs for some purpose that is male specific. Another explanation could be higher activities of piRNAs in female germline than in male germline (Czech *et.al*, 2013). The piRNAs defend against selfish genetics elements and could therefore repress transposon mobility in the ovaries.

One potential reason for this transposon bias in males could be due to male X chromosome hyper-regulation. In males, the X chromosome is upregulated due to sex chromosome dosage compensation. This is done so that the expression of the X-linked genes will be relatively the same between males and females, since if males only get half the amount of protein and RNA from the chromosome, it could lead to dosage problems. However, this upregulation could mean that the TEs get upregulated as well, perhaps by association. Since all of the male biased regions in the fly are on the X chromosome, this seems like a reasonable explanation. This could also be due to the fact the sex chromosome experience very different epigenetic regulatory controls. However, that does not mean that the increase in TEs is detrimental to the male flies. At the very least, they are neutral, since male flies function perfectly normally with this increase in transposon mobility. Since I have been analyzing genomic data, the increase in copy number of transposon DNA seems to be best explained by an increase in the transposon mobility.

One way to test this theory would be to create flies with the male biased transposons moved to another chromosome. If the TE is completely moved to a new location in the genome, it should be possible to determine if the TE remains male biased. By moving the transposon to a new chromosome, it will no longer be under the influence of the X-specific epigenetic influences and upregulation. This means that if the male TE bias is due to X upregulation, the bias should disappear with the TE on a new chromosome. However, this could also be due to dissociation of the regulatory mechanisms controlling these TEs. Therefore, another way to test if the upregulation of the TEs in males is due to sex chromosome dosage compensation would be to remove the dosage compensation from males. This will obviously lead to other problems, but presumably there will have been enough time for the TEs to activate before the fly dies. Therefore, if there is no male bias, this could be more evidence that the X upregulation is the reason for the male TE bias.

One of the more concerning things I have discovered with this analysis is the large difference between the analysis with the version 5.54 genome and the version 6.01 genome. Not only did the amount of mappable heterochromatin-associated DNA sequences change, the new genome allowed for more reads mapping to TEs within the X chromosome. This clearly shows that our ability to create accurate reference genomes cannot necessarily keep up with the need for them. Moreover, full genome analyses done on organisms even

with the most advanced reference genomes can miss important factors that contribute to genome biology. Therefore, there are more than likely a number of genomic analyses that are missing important information that may never be found if no one runs the analyses with either the new or old genome assembly. Care should be taken in performing multi-reference and de novo analyses to validate CNVs at the genome-scale.

Table 1. All used *D. melanogaster* lines and GEO accession numbers. Shows all the used *D. melanogaster* lines from the DrosDel data set as well as the white eye mutation line. Also shows the deletion coordinates for each line.

DrosDel ID	GEO Accession	Deletion coordinates	URL
w1118	GSM783089	w1118 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783089
w1118	GSM783090	w1118 M ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783090
Df(2L)ED2809	GSM783091	2L:67365..72671 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783091
Df(2L)ED2809	GSM783092	2L:67365..72671 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783092
Df(2L)ED62	GSM783093	2L:480873..826788 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783093
Df(2L)ED62	GSM783094	2L:480873..826788 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783094
Df(2L)ED80	GSM783095	2L:568095..850645 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783095
Df(2L)ED80	GSM783096	2L:568095..850645 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783096
Df(2L)ED87	GSM783097	2L:568095..852827 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783097
Df(2L)ED87	GSM783098	2L:568095..852827 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783098

Df(2L)EDHsp60cED478	GSM783099	2L:7437441..7576637 and 2L:5660000..5670000 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783099
Df(2L)EDHsp60cED478	GSM783100	2L:7437441..7576637 and 2L:5660000..5670000 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783100
Df(2L)ED280	GSM783101	2L:5801930..5907456 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783101
Df(2L)ED280	GSM783102	2L:5801930..5907456 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783102
Df(2L)ED292	GSM783103	2L:5801930..5981009 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783103
Df(2L)ED292	GSM783104	2L:5801930..5981009 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783104
Df(2L)ED385	GSM783105	2L:5980272..6465772 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783105
Df(2L)ED385	GSM783106	2L:5980272..6465772 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783106
Df(2L)ED7007	GSM783107	2L:6709099..6963808 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783107
Df(2L)ED7007	GSM783108	2L:6709099..6963808 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783108
Df(2L)ED489	GSM783109	2L:7204186..7576637 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783109
Df(2L)ED489	GSM783110	2L:7204186..7576637 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783110
Df(2L)ED499	GSM783111	2L:7423765..7800182 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783111
Df(2L)ED499	GSM783112	2L:7423765..7800182 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783112

Df(2L)ED475	GSM783113	2L:7423915..7576637 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783113
Df(2L)ED475	GSM783114	2L:7423915..7576637 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783114
Df(2L)ED623	GSM783115	2L:8403564..8700124 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783115
Df(2L)ED623	GSM783116	2L:8403564..8700124 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783116
Df(2L)ED695	GSM783117	2L:9699225..9918192 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783117
Df(2L)ED695	GSM783118	2L:9699225..9918192 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783118
Df(2L)ED775	GSM783119	2L:12010010..12975028 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783119
Df(2L)ED775	GSM783120	2L:12010010..12975028 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783120
Df(2L)ED776	GSM783121	2L:12434538..12975028 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783121
Df(2L)ED776	GSM783122	2L:12434538..12975028 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783122
Df(2L)ED777	GSM783123	2L:12484452..12975028 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783123
Df(2L)ED777	GSM783124	2L:12484452..12975028 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783124
Df(2L)ED793	GSM783125	2L:13934848..14689337 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783125
Df(2L)ED793	GSM783126	2L:13934848..14689337 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783126

Df(2L)ED800	GSM783127	2L:14490575..15332688 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783127
Df(2L)ED800	GSM783128	2L:14490575..15332688 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783128
Df(2L)ED1231	GSM783129	2L:19158440..19464056 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783129
Df(2L)ED1231	GSM783130	2L:19158440..19464056 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783130
Df(2L)ED1305	GSM783131	2L:20085397..20382385 ♀	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783131
Df(2L)ED1305	GSM783132	2L:20085397..20382385 ♂	http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSM783132

Table 2. Number of bases mapped on five samples with different mapping tools and options.

Shows the differences between the three mapping tools and their options in terms of number of bases covered by mapped reads in the genome. ¹There was an error that occurred in two of the Bowtie 2 samples that corrupted the data for those two samples, making it impossible to get data.

Mapping tool	Commands used	Sample	Number of bases mapped
Bowtie 2	default	w1118 ♀	104103452
Bowtie 2	--rfg 3,1	w1118 ♀	104243753
Bowtie 2	--rdg 3,1	w1118 ♀	104299743
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive	w1118 ♀	104374376
Bowtie 2	--local	w1118 ♀	104884639
Bowtie 2	--local --no-unal	w1118 ♀	104145292
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive-local --no-unal	w1118 ♀	104975735
SHRiMP	default	w1118 ♀	106761082
SHRiMP	-g 3 -e 1	w1118 ♀	21904888
SHRiMP	--single-best-mapping	w1118 ♀	105488217

SHRiMP	--max-alignments 3	w1118 ♀	100492262
BWA	default	w1118 ♀	103239382
Bowtie 2	default	w1118 ♂	105579702
Bowtie 2	--rfg 3,1	w1118 ♂	105709024
Bowtie 2	--rdg 3,1	w1118 ♂	105766875
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive	w1118 ♂	105799525
Bowtie 2	--local	w1118 ♂	106305231
Bowtie 2	--local --no-unal	w1118 ♂	105767733
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive-local --no-unal	w1118 ♂	106377404
SHRiMP	default	w1118 ♂	108093077
SHRiMP	-g 3 -e 1	w1118 ♂	22813961
SHRiMP	--single-best-mapping	w1118 ♂	106385310
SHRiMP	--max-alignments 3	w1118 ♂	100834054
BWA	default	w1118 ♂	104403975
Bowtie 2	default	ED2809 ♀	110722765
Bowtie 2	--rfg 3,1	ED2809 ♀	110866036
Bowtie 2	--rdg 3,1	ED2809 ♀	110909097
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive	ED2809 ♀	110891266
Bowtie 2	--local	ED2809 ♀	111488663
Bowtie 2	--local --no-unal	ED2809 ♀	111068741
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive-local --no-unal	ED2809 ♀	111547542
SHRiMP	default	ED2809 ♀	112954795
SHRiMP	-g 3 -e 1	ED2809 ♀	25073290
SHRiMP	--single-best-mapping	ED2809 ♀	111628701
SHRiMP	--max-alignments 3	ED2809 ♀	106775988

BWA	default	ED2809 ♀	109999568
Bowtie 2	default	ED2809 ♂	104207310
Bowtie 2	--rfg 3,1	ED2809 ♂	104350413
Bowtie 2	--rdg 3,1	ED2809 ♂	104400138
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive	ED2809 ♂	104383040
Bowtie 2	--local	ED2809 ♂	104999168
Bowtie 2	--local --no-unal	ED2809 ♂	N/A ¹
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive-local --no-unal	ED2809 ♂	105059817
SHRiMP	default	ED2809 ♂	106613383
SHRiMP	-g 3 -e 1	ED2809 ♂	20842039
SHRiMP	--single-best-mapping	ED2809 ♂	104880331
SHRiMP	--max-alignments 3	ED2809 ♂	99313934
BWA	default	ED2809 ♂	103143344
Bowtie 2	default	ED62 ♀	113423451
Bowtie 2	--rfg 3,1	ED62 ♀	113554059
Bowtie 2	--rdg 3,1	ED62 ♀	113584990
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive	ED62 ♀	113564547
Bowtie 2	--local	ED62 ♀	114041443
Bowtie 2	--local --no-unal	ED62 ♀	N/A ¹
Bowtie 2	--very-sensitive-local --no-unal	ED62 ♀	114087481
SHRiMP	default	ED62 ♀	115300529
SHRiMP	-g 3 -e 1	ED62 ♀	28235079
SHRiMP	--single-best-mapping	ED62 ♀	113925075
SHRiMP	--max-alignments 3	ED62 ♀	109162831
BWA	default	ED62 ♀	112511928

Table 3. Final comparison of mapping tools. Shows the differences between the percentage of deletions, insertions, SNPs, and total alternate calls out of the whole genome for each mapping tool. Also shows the difference between the tools for the number of mapped bases and reads. Bowtie 2 is represented by bt2, BWA by bwa, and SHRiMP by shr in the mapping tool column.

Line	Mapping Tool	Percent Deletions	Percent Insertions	Percent SNPs	Percent Total Alternate Calls	Number of mapped bases	Number of mapped reads
w1118 ♀	bt2	3.55e-6	2.46e-6	1.92e-3	1.93e-3	104145292	8141724
w1118 ♀	bwa	9.95e-6	9.21e-6	2.72e-3	2.74e-3	103239382	8074708
w1118 ♀	shr	2.35e-5	2.10e-5	3.82e-3	3.86e-3	100492262	7863782
w1118 ♂	bt2	4.48e-6	2.92e-6	2.06e-3	2.07e-3	105767733	8753280
w1118 ♂	bwa	1.16e-5	1.03e-5	2.83e-3	2.85e-3	104403975	8630156
w1118 ♂	shr	2.64e-5	2.18e-5	3.86e-3	3.91e-3	100834054	8361191
ED2809 ♀	bt2	1.19e-5	8.65e-6	2.48e-3	2.50e-3	111068741	11424790
ED2809 ♀	bwa	2.79e-5	2.72e-5	3.27e-3	3.32e-3	109999568	11286753
ED2809 ♀	shr	5.90e-5	5.31e-5	4.51e-3	4.62e-3	106775988	10936562
ED2809 ♂	bwa	2.28e-5	2.25e-5	3.00e-3	3.05e-3	103143344	9303994
ED2809 ♂	shr	5.07e-5	5.11e-5	4.32e-3	4.42e-3	99313934	8925644
ED62 ♀	bwa	5.52e-5	5.42e-5	3.66e-3	3.77e-3	112511928	15115555

ED62 ♀	shr	1.12e-4	1.05e-4	4.99e-3	5.21e-3	109162831	14642007
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